

ACTUAL ASPECTS OF IMPROVING LEGISLATION COMPULSORY INSURANCE IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: The article highlights the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the provision of compulsory insurance services and proposes their improvement.

Keywords: insurance, insurance activity, development of insurance, the role and significance of insurance.

Uzbekistan is consistently following its own chosen path of development - the creation of an open market economy towards a strongly legal democratic state. The theoretical foundations of the deeply thought-out socio-economic and political transformations carried out in the country over the past years, as well as the practical program for their implementation, are outlined in the works of the President of the Republic, in which special attention is focused on an integral part of the market infrastructure - the insurance services market [1].

As you know, one of the priority areas of economic reforms in Uzbekistan is the creation of the necessary conditions for doing business. Its success is inextricably linked with the institutions of a market economy, in particular, the development of modern forms and services of insurance at a high level.

Uzbekistan has created a solid legislative framework in the field of insurance services that corresponds with international standards.

On the international insurance market, the sphere of compulsory passenger insurance is widely developed in all types of passenger transport, including air, rail, road and inland waterways, as well as international transportation. On May 26, 2015, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On compulsory insurance of the carrier's civil liability” was adopted. This legal act not only expands the market of insurance services, but also creates additional guarantees for the protection of life, health and property of citizens.

In accordance with the content of compulsory passenger insurance, financial protection is provided for victims during transportation and payment is guaranteed in case of damage to life, health or property. According to the contract of compulsory insurance of civil liability of the carrier, the organization engaged in transportation assumes responsibility for the safe delivery of the passenger to the intended address.

Prior to the adoption of this legal act, the conclusion of an insurance contract for compensation for damage caused during transportation was entrusted to passengers.

Currently, transport organizations for the carriage of passengers must insure their liability to passengers, who, if necessary, have the right to receive compensation for damage from the carrier. That is, in case of traffic accidents, a mechanism is provided for guaranteed payment to the passenger for the harm caused by transport enterprises.

There are a number of scientific and practical opinions about the compulsory insurance of civil liability of transport enterprises.

In particular, K. Rashidov in his works notes that in international transportation, the degree of harm to passengers, also to a third party, is quite high, therefore, in such cases, insurance is developed and has a strong legal regulation. Such transportation is currently carried out in the case of compulsory insurance of the carrier's legal liability.

Meanwhile, K. Rashidov argues the connection between the carrier and the insurer, as well as their interaction as follows: “as much as the responsibility of

transport enterprises is significant, the insurance of the carrier will be so important. In addition, there is such a notion that, according to the content of the insurance of the owner of the cargo and carriers, it seems necessary to insure the liability of the transport organization. In general, liability insurance for the carrier, cargo owner and passenger will not be required [2].

According to Russian scientists M.I. Braginsky and V.V. Vitryansky, while transporting passengers on a voluntary basis, an agreement is concluded on compulsory life and health insurance, and compulsory insurance of civil legal liability to a third party is carried out between transport enterprises and insurance organizations [3].

In accordance with the abovementioned scientific and practical judgments, the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On compulsory insurance of the carrier’s civil liability” is very relevant, which became the basis for the denunciation of the Law “On compulsory personal insurance of passengers of air, rail, inland water and motor transport for general use”.

The reforms carried out in the field of insurance are another confirmation of ensuring the protection of human rights and interests. Since, in accordance with Article 922 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, an obligation is established to insure the life, health or property of other persons specified in the law in case of harm to their life, health or property.

Today in Uzbekistan, the adoption of another law aimed at regulating relations in insurance activities is a vital task.

When analyzing the tasks and responsibilities of the parties to a contract of compulsory liability insurance (state compulsory), in practice there is a different performance of their duties by individuals and legal entities who are obliged to conclude a contract of compulsory insurance and for this reason there are no identical measures of responsibility for not concluding such contracts of insurance. In particular, according to Article 18 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On bankruptcy”, Article 28 of the Law “On protection of consumer rights” and

Article 5 of the Law “On auditing”, financial service providers, as well as audit organizations, must insure their civil liability without fail. In a number of legislative acts, despite the fact that such an obligation is imposed on some individuals or legal entities, no measures are provided for its non-fulfillment.

For example, in case of violation of the laws “On compulsory insurance of civil legal liability of an employer”, “On compulsory insurance of civil legal liability of transport owners” and the Law “On compulsory insurance of civil liability of the carrier” adopted on May 26, 2015, in articles 49-2, 135- 1, 146- 1 of Administrative Responsibility Code does not define measures of administrative punishment, due to which the same law enforcement practice of this type of compulsory insurance is applied.

Consistent introduction into the Administrative Responsibility Code of individual measures of liability in relation to individuals or legal entities who need to insure their civil legal liability on a mandatory basis leads to an artificial increase in its volume.

In the Code of the Russian Federation on Administrative Offenses, such liability measures are distributed by type of insurance.

In order to ensure equal performance of compulsory insurance and exclude the above problems, it seems necessary to adopt the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the implementation of compulsory (state compulsory) insurance”. In this legal act, it is important to fix the rules regarding the procedure for concluding a compulsory insurance contract, strengthening the liability of individuals or legal entities, their obligations when concluding it and legal liability. Also, in the relevant article of the Administrative Responsibility Code, it is necessary to introduce a rule on liability for failure to conclude or for its untimely preparation by persons who are obliged to conclude a binding or state contract. That is, the measure of responsibility enshrined in one article provides for general responsibility for the failure by individuals or legal entities that have the right to conclude a binding (state binding) contract, this responsibility. This will allow, in the application of liability to

individuals or legal entities who have not fulfilled their obligations, to follow the principles of transparency and equality, as well as the specific and uniform implementation of laws.

This practice is enshrined in Article 11.64 of the Code of Administrative Offenses of the Republic of Belarus, Article 305 of the Code of Offenses of the Republic of Moldova, Articles 310-311 of the Code of Administrative Offenses of the Republic of Turkmenistan. Namely, in Article 310 of the Code of Administrative Offenses of the Republic of Turkmenistan measures of responsibility for non-compliance with the provisions of compulsory insurance are determined.

The above proposed law was adopted by the Russian Federation, which is currently considered an important document regulating relations when concluding a mandatory (state mandatory) insurance contract.

The adoption of such a law in the Republic of Uzbekistan will serve the same and exact execution of mandatory and state binding contracts in the field of insurance, the effective provision of the rights and freedoms of citizens in the provision of insurance services.

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